

USING THE "CLUSTER" METHOD TO DEVELOP CRITICAL THINKING IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20791046>

Abstract

This article discusses the advantages of the "Cluster" method used in developing critical thinking in preschool-aged children, as well as the stages and results of applying this method.

Keywords: critical thinking, critical thinking, intellectual ability, "Cluster" method, visual brainstorming.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются преимущества метода «Кластер», используемого в развитии критического мышления детей дошкольного возраста, этапы и результаты использования этого метода.

Ключевые слова: критическое мышление, критическое мышление, интеллектуальные способности, метод «Кластер», визуальный мозговой штурм.

It is extremely difficult to motivate today's modern young generation to engage in cognitive activity and to find a path to a goal in the information and communication sphere. Children of preschool age, upon entering preschool education, often encounter serious difficulties at the stage of perceiving educational material in all preschool subjects. This is due to the fact that thinking, and primarily critical thinking, is not developed at a sufficiently high level, and this is very important for a person entering a new century in the modern world with a new vision of cognitive culture.

Criticism of mind is the ability of a person to objectively evaluate themselves and the opinions of others, the ability to carefully and comprehensively check all put forward rules and conclusions. Critical thinking helps a person determine their priorities in personal and professional life, develops the ability to inform, analyze, and draw independent conclusions, predict the consequences of their decisions, and be responsible for them; it also allows for the development of a culture of communication in joint activities, includes individual responsibility for the chosen choice, and increases the level of individual work culture.

Critical thinking involves the reasoning that led to our conclusions, which are the most important functions of the thinking process, or the self-assessment of factors that we took into account when making decisions. According to M.V. Clarina, critical thinking is rational, reflective thinking aimed at deciding what to

believe or how to act. Understood in this way, critical thinking includes abilities (skills) and inclinations (attitudes).

Critical thinking is one of the types characterized by a high level of human intellectual activity. This term can refer to almost any mental activity. Learning aimed at developing critical thinking skills involves more than just actively seeking information to master: linking what is learned with one's own experiences, as well as comparing what is learned with other research in the field of knowledge. Students have the right to question the reliability or validity of the information received, verify the logicalness of the evidence, draw conclusions, create new examples for its application, consider possibilities for solving the problem, etc.

Scientists note that in our rapidly changing era, associated with the rapid growth of information, the volume of human knowledge in the structure of thinking is increasing at a high rate. But from the perspective of mastering logical laws, the thinking process, as a rule, proceeds automatically. Therefore, the effectiveness of mental activity in preschool children, unfortunately, lags far behind their capabilities and does not fully meet modern educational tasks.

The thinking process begins when a task or problem arises that does not have a ready-made solution. How can one increase motivation for cognitive activity? How to involve preschool children in the educational process? Today, every educator asks these questions. Only the competent use of various teaching methods allows for the creation of conditions that encourage preschoolers to engage in cognitive and research activities. But can you learn to think more effectively? Like other qualities of the mind, thinking can also develop. Developing thinking means developing the ability to think. For the effectiveness of the educational process, the ability to select the correct technological methods, successfully combine them, and adapt them to the range of already familiar traditional forms of instruction is essential.

Critical thinking is a step toward active, creative methods. If we want to raise a child as a capable person, we must not just fill them with information, but encourage them to think critically—that is, draw their own conclusions based on the information obtained, reason, and ask the right questions. To achieve these results, we will consider the "Cluster" method, one of the most common methods for developing critical thinking.

A cluster (English: cluster accumulation) is an association of several identical elements that can be viewed as an independent unit possessing certain properties.

The "Cluster" method, which is a method of graphically organizing material that allows preschoolers to visualize the mental processes that occur when instilling a specific topic, is also called a "visual brainstorming."

"Cluster" is a technique for developing critical thinking technology that allows a child to generalize and systematize material on a specific topic using graphic design.

The main concept—the topic—is written or drawn in the center. Concepts related to the key are drawn or written near the rays extending from the central image (word). Since not all children can read, you can use illustrated or mixed "Clusters" (pictures, photographs, drawings, diagrams). When creating a "cluster," write down everything that comes to mind and try to establish as many connections as possible. Large sheets of paper are enough for the drawings, but if there are many children, you will need to glue a few sheets. The cluster stays in the group for several days, and the children periodically come to it, look at it, and talk to each other. So the children can go back to them if they want to.

The cluster activates the mental activity of preschool children: it develops skills in asking questions, emphasizing the main thing, comparing, establishing cause-and-effect relationships, and drawing conclusions. The versatility of the cluster lies in the fact that this technique can be used by all educators in the entire preschool education system, including educators, speech therapists, psychologists, and other specialists.

When working with clusters, the educator must follow the following rules:

1. Do not be afraid to write down everything that comes to mind.
2. Give freedom to your imagination and intuition.
3. Keep working until you run out of time or ideas.
4. Try to establish as many contacts as possible.
5. Do not follow a predetermined plan.

The steps for creating a cluster are as follows:

Step 1 - write a keyword in the middle of a blank sheet, which is the "heart" of the idea or topic.

Stage 2 - around the word they write everything they remember about this topic - the expression of ideas, facts, images, corresponding to this topic.

Stage 3 - systematization is carried out. Chaotic entries are grouped according to which aspect of the content reflects a specific recorded concept or fact (the "planet and its satellites" model).

Step 4 - words that appear during writing are connected to the main concept through straight lines. Each "satellite" in turn has "satellites," and new logical connections are established.

As a result, a structure emerges that graphically reflects our thoughts and defines the information field of this topic.

The cluster method can be applied during educational activities when studying various topics. When using this method, the form of work can be absolutely any: individual, group, or team. It is determined based on the set goals and objectives, as well as the capabilities of the teacher and the children's collective. It is permissible to flow from one form to another. For example, this could be individual work, where each child creates their own cluster. Upon the emergence of new knowledge, a general graphical diagram is compiled based on individual drawings and taking into account the acquired knowledge as a joint discussion of the material covered. A cluster can be used both as a method of organizing work during educational activities and as an individual task. In the second case, it is important that the preschool educator has some experience in its creation.

The use of a cluster has the following advantages:

- 1) This method allows children to cover a large amount of information;
- 2) involve all members of the team in the educational process, they are interested in it;
- 3) children are active and open, as they are not afraid to make mistakes or make incorrect judgments.

During the use of this method, the following skills are formed and developed in preschool children:

- ability to ask questions;
- emphasize the main point;
- establishing causal relationships and drawing conclusions;
- a holistic understanding of the problem and a transition from the specific to the general;
- comparison and analysis;
- drawing analogies

What benefits does the use of the cluster method bring to preschool children?

The use of clusters develops systemic thinking, teaches children to systematize not only educational material but also their value judgments, teaches children to develop and express their own opinions formed on the basis of

observations, experiences, and acquired new knowledge, and develops skills for considering multiple positions simultaneously and the ability to creatively process information.

Educational activities using the cluster method provide preschoolers with the freedom to express themselves, express their views on the issue, and engage in creative activity. In general, non-traditional technologies used in the educational process increase students' enthusiasm, create an atmosphere of cooperation, and form a sense of self-respect in children, awakening a sense of creative freedom in them..

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